

India's Strategic Advantage in IT/ITeS Industry: A survey of Pune based firms

Vishal Wadajkar¹, Pooja Patil² and Nihal Jaiswal³

¹Deputy Director - Academics, ²Assistant Professor and ³Student,
Dr. D. Y. Patil B-School, Pune, Maharashtra, India

Objectives: This is a descriptive study to assess India's strategic advantage in IT/ITeS industry using a survey questionnaire.

Materials and Methods: Descriptive hypothesis was set and studied based on primary data collected from 100 IT/ITeS industry leaders from Pune who were surveyed for India's strategic advantage. The responses were measured on a 5-point Likert scale for 10 sub-questions. The sample mean was compared against the hypothesized population mean of 50% and was tested for statistical significance at 95% confidence level.

Results: The study disclosed that the India's strategic advantage in IT/ITeS industry was statistically significant. The mean was found to be well above the hypothesized population mean (Mean = 87%; SD = 0.82).

Conclusion: The results of the study indicate that India's strategic advantage in IT/ITeS is significant.

Keywords: Strategic Advantage, IT/ITeS.

Introduction

The worldwide sourcing market in India keeps on growing at a higher rate contrasted with the IT-BPM industry. India is the main sourcing destination across the world, representing around 55% piece of the pie of the US\$ 200–250 billion worldwide sourcing business. Indian IT and BPM organizations have set up more than 1,000 global delivery centers in around 80 nations across the world. India has become the digital capabilities hub of the world with around 75% of global talent present in the country.

India's IT dominance is underpinned by several strategic advantages. Some of the advantages are:

- 1) India has a low-cost advantage by being 5-6 times inexpensive than the US.
- 2) The government has framed National Policy on software products which aims to develop India as a software product nation.
- 3) Indian IT firms have delivery centers all over the world and have well diversified presence across verticals.
- 4) The demand for IT services is strong given the emergence of new technologies such as AI and machine learning.

Given the importance of the IT sector, we decided to survey leaders from IT/ITeS firms to assess India's strategic advantage.

The research question to be addressed is as follows:

RQ: Is India's strategic advantage in IT/ITeS industry significant?

The term "significant" was operationalized at the mid-point of a 5-point Likert scale at the value of 50%.

Literature Review

A book by Krishna et al. (2017) lists twelve success factors including cheap manpower which have led to the success of Indian IT industry.

The paper by Bhattacharjee and Chakrabarti (2015), investigates the factors instrumental in giving a competitive edge to the Indian IT-ITeS sector using Porter's diamond model. The paper ascertains the general superiority of the model in clarifying India's prominence in the IT-ITeS sector. The study carries out a complex use of the model that is "instrumental" in recognizing certain distinct factors under the realms of the diamond, the interplay of which catapulted India into the most preferred outsourcing destination. The study posits that the sector is probably going to hold its innovative prominence in the foreseeable future.

A research by Yadav and Yadav (2017) argues that in a quickly changing competitive world, human resources are one of the critical factors of competitive advantage. Human resources are viewed as the resources of every country, which demonstrated to make competitive advantage contrasted and nations rely upon natural resources. The human resources in the organizations have knowledge, skills and experience which contribute for the development of the associations through competitive advantage. To investigate the huge part of human asset practices in Indian software industry, a survey was directed with different level of employees. The organized poll was ready for this investigation which comprehensively centers around human asset practices, for example, recruitment and selection, training and development, motivation performance and satisfaction. It was seen that software organizations are practicing comparable human resource policies across all levels.

The study by Athreye (2005) examines the development of dynamic capabilities among firms in the Indian software industry by looking in some detail at the changing constraints, opportunities and competition facing incumbent firms. It emphasizes the important role played by tight labor market conditions in inducing investment in process capability and the role of entrepreneurial experimentation in evolving a business model (out-sourced software) that was most appropriate to limited resource advantages of Indian software firms.

A contextual research gap clearly exists and hence this study was undertaken by surveying IT/ITeS industry leaders in Pune.

Methodology

The research methodology adopted is outlined below:

1. A survey questionnaire was administered to 100 (Bullen, 2016) IT/ITeS industry leaders.
2. The selection of the 100 IT/ITeS leaders was based on the judgment of the writer of getting an adequate response in a reasonable time. Convenient sampling was used.
3. The survey questionnaire had ten questions related to the various aspects of India's strategic advantage in IT/ITeS industry.
4. Responses were sought on 5-point Likert-scale.
5. For assessment of India's strategic advantage, the scale used was: 0- Can't say, 1- somewhat agree, 2- strongly agree, 3- somewhat disagree, 4- strongly disagree. The 10 sub-questions were: 1 – young population, 2 – engineering graduates, 3 – English speaking resource, 4 – pricing, 5 – experience of firms, 6 – domain experience, 7 – broad range of services, 8 – consulting services, 9- outsourcing trend, and 10 – lack of qualified manpower in importing countries.

Statement of Hypothesis:

Ho1: India's strategic advantage in IT/ITeS industry is not significant

Ha1: India's strategic advantage in IT/ITeS industry is significant

Data analysis included descriptive analysis specifying features of the sample and the inferential analysis to test the hypothesis. A t-test was used given the fact that the SD of the population is not known, in which case, a Z-test could have been applied. The use of a t-test in practice is widely done as a substitute for the Z-test wherein the SD of the sample is taken as the SD of the population (given unknown population SD).

The survey instrument returned a Cronbach's alpha of 0.9530 that is better than 0.70 (the standard) and hence was considered as reliable.

Data Analysis

Descriptive analysis:

70 out of the 100 IT/ITeS industry leaders were male while 30 were female. 39 users belonged to the age-group <30 years, 38 were from the age-group 30-40, while 23 were from the age-group >40 years. 15 users had experience in the range of <10 years, 62 in the range of 10-15 years, and 23 were having experience of more than 15 years.

Inferential analysis:

The null hypothesis was set as the sample mean ($\bar{x}$) equals the hypothesized population mean (μ). The alternate hypothesis was: $H_a1: \bar{x} > 50\%$.

Summary of the ratings for India's strategic advantage are given in Table 1 below:

Table 1: Summary of responses for customer satisfaction of internet banking users

Concepts	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	Total
Average Agreement	90%	89%	81%	86%	91%	81%	83%	87%	91%	86%	87%

Table 2 shows the testing of the hypothesis at 95% confidence level.

Table 2: Testing of the hypothesis

Parameter	H1 value
Sample Mean ($\bar{x}$)	87%
Hypothesized population mean (μ)	50%
SD of sample	0.82
n (sample size)	100
t-value= $\text{abs}((\bar{x} - \mu) / (s/\sqrt{n}))$	4.48
p-value = $\text{tdist}(t,(n-1),1)$	0.00001
Decision	Reject Null

The null hypothesis was rejected in favor of the alternate that the sample mean is significantly different from the hypothesized population mean.

Discussion on results

The sample mean for the agreement on India's strategic advantage was 87% (SD = 0.82) and was significantly higher than a midpoint of 50% agreement.

Conclusion

The research shows that India's strategic advantage in IT/ITeS industry is significant. There are several factors which support this advantage and there is broad consensus that these factors will continue to benefit IT/ITeS sector growth.

As the study was based on sampling, limitations of sampling, in general, are applicable to it as well. Researchers are encouraged to study specific attributes of strategic advantage which will add to the earlier research.

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